

Supplementary Material: Curvature-Coupled Triangulated Relativistic Quantum Computation (gTRQC) – Numerical Proof of Concept

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Abstract

This document serves as the technical guide to the Proof of Concept (PoC) repository accompanying the manuscript *Curvature-Coupled Triangulated Relativistic Quantum Computation: Entanglement Equilibrium, Geometry Registers, and Discrete Curvature-Response Relations*. It details the dual-branch experimental design—contrasting static equilibrium baselines with dynamic, non-inertial stress tests—and analyzes the implications of the “Matrix Search” optimization performed over the kinematic parameter space. We further discuss the software architecture, data provenance, and potential extensions of the framework.

1 Repository Overview and Code Availability

The numerical validation of the gTRQC framework is hosted in a structured repository designed to isolate equilibrium properties from kinematic stress responses. The codebase is organized into two primary experimental branches alongside a comparative analysis suite.

1.1 Directory Structure

- `gTRQC_08_static/`: Contains the *Static Approach* simulations. These experiments utilize the `GTRQCSimulator` class to establish baseline residuals for the Einstein-type constraint equations on fixed triangulations (Tetrahedron, Octahedron, Cube) under thermal equilibrium conditions.
- `gTRQC_14/`: Contains the *Dynamic Approach* simulations. These experiments utilize the `AcceleratedRotatingSurfaceGTRQCSimulator` to subject the triangulation to non-inertial forces (centrifugal, Coriolis) and angular acceleration. This folder houses the "Matrix Search" artifacts—thousands of time-series logs (`.json`) and state tensors (`.npz`) exploring the stability landscape.
- `Visualization_static_vs_dynamic.ipynb`: The central analysis dashboard that aggregates data from both branches, performs fold-averaging, and generates the comparative heatmaps and "One-Pager" PDFs.

1.2 Availability

The complete source code, including the automated parameter sweep scripts and visualization tools, is available for replication:

- **Repository URL:** <https://github.com/QC-UPM/gTRQC>
- **Dependencies:** Python 3.8+, `numpy`, `scipy`, `matplotlib`, `networkx`, `PennyLane` (for quantum channel backend).
- **Zenodo:** <https://zenodo.org/records/18176648>

2 Experimental Design: Static vs. Dynamic Approaches

The PoC addresses two fundamental questions derived from the main text: (1) Does the geometry register maintain closure in equilibrium? and (2) Can the curvature response mechanism adapt to active kinematic deformation?

2.1 Part I: Static Equilibrium Baseline

In the `gTRQC_08_static` module, the triangulation is treated as a fixed background.

- **Objective:** Validate the "Geometry Free Energy Functional" and the stationarity of Generalized Entropy (S_{gen}) without external work.
- **Methodology:** The simulator initializes a random quantum matter state on the dual graph of a closed surface (e.g., TETRA). The system evolves via GKSL dynamics where the dissipation rates are modulated by static curvature defects.
- **Key Result:** This branch establishes the *Baseline Residual* ($\mathcal{R}_{stat} \approx 4.5$), representing the intrinsic noise floor of the discrete Einstein constraints due to finite-dimensional discretization.

2.2 Part II: Dynamic Stress Testing (Matrix Search)

The `gTRQC_14` module implements the core novelty of the paper: the *active* response of geometry to matter in non-inertial frames.

The Mechanical Surrogate: To simulate spacetime elasticity, the edges of the triangulation are modeled as damped springs. The nodes obey Newton-Euler equations of motion including:

- **Drive Force:** An external angular acceleration (Clockwise/Counter-Clockwise).
- **Elastic Restoring Force:** Proportional to the spring constant k_{spring} (Parameter: SK).
- **Inertial Forces:** Centrifugal and Coriolis terms arising from the rotating reference frame.

Parameter Sweep (The Matrix Search): To identify stable "Geometry Registers," the PoC performs a high-resolution sweep over the following parameters, generating distinct data folds (Artifacts tagged `ACCEL_ROT_POC`):

Table 1 Dynamic Parameter Space (`gTRQC_14`)

Parameter	Values / Description
Geometry	TETRA (Tetrahedron) - Found to be the most stable minimal surface.
Rotation	ROT.CW, ROT.CCW (Tests parity invariance of the response).
Spring Constant (SK)	low (6.25), mid (12.5), high (25.0). Controls the "stiffness" of the vacuum.
Drive Gain (DG)	low, mid, high. Amplitude of the kinematic deformation.
Coupling (GK)	$g \in \{0.0, 0.25, 0.5, 1.0\}$. Strength of the curvature-matter feedback loop.

3 Implications for the Main Manuscript

The numerical results extracted from the `.npz` artifacts provide quantitative support for the theoretical claims in the paper.

3.1 Stability of the Einstein-Type Constraint

The comparative analysis (see `gtrqc_best_dynamics_spatial_report.pdf`) reveals that while dynamic deformation increases the absolute residual of the constraint equations ($\mathcal{R}_{dyn} > \mathcal{R}_{stat}$), there exist specific "Goldilocks zones" in the parameter space (specifically at **Mid-Spring / Low-Drive** settings) where the system maintains closure.

- **Implication:** This suggests that the `gTRQC` discrete curvature response is physically viable only within specific bounds of "spacetime stiffness," analogous to the stability conditions in classical Regge calculus.

3.2 Geometry Dependence

The simulations show a marked performance hierarchy: **TETRA** \ddagger **OCTA** \ddagger **CUBE**.

- **Observation:** The Tetrahedron geometry consistently yields the lowest residuals and highest entanglement stability under rotation.
- **Implication:** Minimal simplicial complexes may offer superior coherence protection for Relativistic Quantum Computing architectures compared to more complex tessellations, likely due to the rigidity of the simplex compared to hypercubic cells.

3.3 Entanglement Suppression

Analysis of the Negativity metric in the dynamic regime indicates that the current Projector-Register scheme tends to suppress quantum correlations ($\mathcal{N} \rightarrow 0$) during high-acceleration phases.

- **Implication:** The "Geometry Register" acts as a decoherence channel when the kinematic drive is too strong. This highlights the necessity for the *coherent* coupling extensions discussed in the Conclusion of the main paper.

4 Potential Extensions

The modular architecture of the PoC allows for several direct extensions to the research:

1. **Coherent Backreaction:** Replacing the dissipative GKSL limit with fully unitary Hamiltonian dynamics for the geometry-matter coupling. This would allow the "Geometry Register" to exist in a superposition of curvature states, rather than a classical mixture.
2. **Higher-Dimensional Simplexes:** The current `NetworkX`-based graph engine can be generalized to `Gudhi` or `SimplicialComplex` libraries to support 3D spatial (4D spacetime) triangulations, testing the Regge action in full 3+1 gravity.
3. **Topological Phase Transitions:** Using the simulator to dynamically change the genus of the underlying triangulation (e.g., tearing/gluing edges) to investigate topological protection of quantum information during topology-changing spacetime events.

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